

Incorporating Spatially Explicit Landscape & Connectivity Metrics Improves the Predictive Ability of Species Distribution Models

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Summary

Species distribution models are one of the most important GIScience research areas in biodiversity. However, models rarely incorporate spatially explicit landscape metrics. Here, we investigated the importance of these features in determining the fine-scale spatial distribution of the critically endangered Eurasian curlew (*Numenius arquata*). Tracking data for 18 birds were collected, a high-resolution land cover map was generated from Sentinel 2 imagery, and the land cover was parameterised using proportions, as well as connectivity metrics using a moving window of 1km. Accounting for the spatial configuration of the landscape generally improved the predictions of habitat preferences beyond the widely employed proportion of suitable land cover.

KEYWORDS: Biogeography; Landscape Metrics; Remote Sensing; Spatial Modelling; Telemetry Data

1. Introduction

Species distribution models (SDMs) are one of the most important GIScience research areas in biogeography and the primary method used to study the potential effects of climate change on species' distributions and ranges (Miller et al. 2020). SDMs provide a methodological framework for researchers and practitioners to quantitatively assess the relationship between species distributions and environmental factors. SDMs project relationships in both environmental and geographic space using different statistical methods and machine learning approaches. Environmental data predominantly includes representations of climate, but for many mobile animals, the use of a focal statistic summarizing the climate and habitat conditions within a specified neighborhood may better represent what is available to it (Holloway and Miller 2017). For example, black grouse use different habitats for mating (moorland) and shelter (woodland), with Geary et al. (2013) identifying that the proportion of different habitats within a neighbourhood improved the statistical model.

However, to-date most models that are parameterised with habitat variables only account for the proportion of land cover within a grid, and do not consider the spatial configuration of the landscape. For example, Figure 1 shows three different landscapes across a 1km x 1km area, with each cell representing one of two land cover types. The number of green cells in the 1km² area is the same in all three landscapes, which means in any statistical model that incorporates proportion of a suitable land cover, they would all have the value 0.25. This is despite the fact they represent greatly different mosaics. Landscape metrics have a long history in landscape ecology and GIScience (Kupfer 2012), yet they have seldom been used in SDM (Hasui et al. 2017). Ignoring landscape configuration in

statistical parameterisation can result in several conceptual and methodological issues that introduce uncertainty, such as static representation of environmental combinations, incorrect species-environmental preferences, and unpredictable feedback related to land cover change. Here we address the research question of whether metrics representing the configuration of the landscape improve species distribution models for a highly mobile species.

Figure 1 Example of different landscape configurations, which all have a combination of 0.75 orange (darker colour) and 0.25 green (lighter colour) grid cells.

2. Methods

Here, we explore the habitat factors that are important in determining the fine-scale spatial distribution of Eurasian curlew at three case study locations, Ballyteige Bay, Co. Wexford, Ireland, the Dyfi Estuary and the Cefni valley, Wales. Tracking data for 18 birds across all three locations were collected across winters 2020 and 2021, at 15-minute intervals for a period of up to four months (Nov-Feb). This equates to approximately 221,000 spatially explicit locations. The species data were filtered using the ‘best-daily location’ method (see Holloway & Miller 2017) and incorporated into a species distribution modelling ensemble approach in R (Thuiller et al. 2009).

Land cover data from Sentinel-2 was generated using a machine learning classification framework, in this instance the Random Forest algorithm. This supervised classification resulted in a high resolution (10m) map of 14 different land covers, which included estuaries, fields, and saltmarshes. Land cover was subsequently incorporated in the models both as proportion of land cover within a neighbourhood (PLAND in Figure 2) as well as a function of habitat connectivity and fragmentation (LPI, PLADJ, CONTIG, & FRAC in Figure 2) using a moving window approach to quantifying landscape metrics. The moving window distance was set to 1km resolution to match the typical resolution of most environmental variables in SDM.

Figure 2 Example of landscape metrics for Ballyteige, land cover class saltmarsh, including proportion of land cover (PLAND), largest patch index (LPI), proportion of adjacent patches (PLADJ), contiguity (CONTIG) and fractal dimensions (FRAC).

3. Results

Results indicate that accounting for the complex spatial configuration of the landscape improves spatial predictions of fine-scale habitat preferences beyond the widely employed proportion of suitable land cover. Table 1 highlights the most accurate models, parameterised on proportion of land cover, landscape metrics, and a combination of both variables. For models parameterised on the landscape metrics, key diurnal differences were identified (Figure 3), as well as slight differences in the variable importance. For models fitted during daylight, connected and large saltmarshes were consistently important in the final models, as well as connected locations of various grasslands. At night, connectivity of saltmarsh and grasslands were the most important variables, as well as connectivity of built and woodland habitats, which the birds are avoiding (but not isolated and unconnected built-up areas).

Table 1 Accuracy metrics for models parameterised for the full dataset, and day and night distributions at Ballyteige (Ireland) and Dyfi (Wales). The most accurate model result is shown in bold. PLAND: Proportion of Land Cover, LMET: Landscape Metrics, Both: Combination. AUC: Area Under the Curve, TSS: True Skill Statistic.

Ballyteige									
	All			Day			Night		
	PLAND	LMET	BOTH	PLAND	LMET	BOTH	PLAND	LMET	BOTH
AUC	0.9987	0.9983	0.9987	0.9980	0.9983	0.9980	0.9977	0.9983	0.9983
TSS	0.9783	0.9793	0.9783	0.9723	0.9747	0.9727	0.9717	0.9810	0.9777
KAPPA	0.9770	0.9770	0.9763	0.9697	0.9700	0.9697	0.9677	0.9777	0.9723
Dyfi									
	All			Day			Night		
	PLAND	LMET	BOTH	PLAND	LMET	BOTH	PLAND	LMET	BOTH
AUC	0.9963	0.9950	0.9953	0.9963	0.9967	0.9275	0.9960	0.9960	0.9963
TSS	0.9700	0.9623	0.9653	0.9700	0.9667	0.8302	0.9707	0.9720	0.9663
KAPPA	0.9447	0.9350	0.933	0.9447	0.9390	0.8197	0.9473	0.9463	0.9363

Figure 3 Habitat Suitability of Eurasian curlew during the a) day and b) night at Ballyteige Ireland, as well as during the c) day and d) night at the Dyfi Estuary, Wales.

4. Recommendations

The Eurasian curlew is classified as globally Near Threatened, and in the UK and Ireland as Critically Endangered. Habitat degradation and loss is often cited as one of the primary drivers of Eurasian curlew decline, yet research has disproportionately focused on the breeding distribution of the species, despite the important role that Irish and UK coastlines play to the global population of wintering Eurasian curlew (Kenobi et al. 2023). The incorporation of landscape metrics through spatial analysis has identified key landscape configuration patterns that influence the wintering distribution, which has supported decision makers in identifying that larger areas of foraging habitat (Marsh / Grassland / Mudflat) are required, and where possible these should increase local connectivity. The diurnal pattern at night also shows a preference to avoid built and wooded areas, more so than during the day, most likely due to predation (dogs, foxes). These results highlight the benefits of advancing the GIScience methods to support applied research questions.

5. References

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